

2.3.2 Life cycle inventory

Vehicle production

The life cycle inventory was prepared by considering the large number of data provided by the manufacturer, on the basis of the structure of the plant, which is described in detail hereafter.

The core processes include all the assembling phases. The assembly mainly takes place in Plant 1 (UP 7), and partially in Plant 2 (UP 8) and Plant 3 (UP 9).

The production in Plant 1 (UP 7) begins in the Welding Shop, where the body is assembled. The components are metal sheets. In the first phase, lateral panels and floors are welded together, and then the cubing welding phase takes place in which the doors and hood are welded to form the body of the vehicle. The loading, handling and welding phases are all mechanized and performed by robots. After the quality controls, the body enters the Painting Shop, but if the body fails the controls it is sent to the recovery section.

In the Painting Shop, the body is washed and then undergoes a cataphoresis treatment. This process involves the electro-deposition of paint by means of immersion under a continuous electrical current. The deposited film is acrylic or epossidic resin, and it confers an elevated anticorrosive property to the body. This process ends with the drying of the body at a high temperature (150 °C – 180 °C). The body is then sealed with polyurethane sealants and painted by robots.

The next phases consist of the assembly of the components. Such components as the dashboard, seats, etc...are installed on the body of the vehicle during the trimming phase. The Body Work phase, in which the chassis, powertrain, driveline and after-treatment system are assembled and then combined with the body from the trimming phase, takes place at the same time. (the Body Work phase also includes the windshield, mirrors, headlights, etc.).

After all these operations, the vehicle is complete and is sent to the testing area, where the alignment and the hydraulic tests are performed. Tests on the bench are also performed in this area. After the tests, the vehicle is finished and is transferred to the commercial park, where it is ready to be placed on the market.

During the bodywork phase, the CNG vehicle and the BEV are transferred to plant 2 (UP 8) and plant 3 (UP9), respectively. The CNG tanks and pipes are installed on the vehicle at plant 2 (UP8). The total capacity of the tanks is 246 lt. The vehicle is then returned to Plant 1, where the assembly process continues. The electrification process of the BEV takes place at plant 3 (UP9). This process consists of the assembly of all the components related to the electric powertrain system: the on-board battery chargers (the vehicle is equipped with a 3.5 kW charger, which is used as standard charger, and 22 kW charger, which is included as an option for fast charging), the batteries, the supercapacitor, the traction inverter and the driveline RG 40-80 kW. The supercapacitor is an electric storage devices that can store a large amount of power and release it quickly; it is used as an ancillary device to recover energy from braking and to provide the necessary boost during quick accelerations [57]. This process also involves the assembly of the auxiliaries: the cooling system (pipes, fans, dual stage pump 205 CV), the high voltage heater (HVH), the Electric Hydraulic Power Steering (EHPS) and the DC/DC converters. After the electrification stage, the BEV is

returned to Plant 1 for final assembly and tests. The Diesel vehicle is assembled entirely at Plant 1.

The authors were provided with the bill of materials (BOM) from the manufacturer for the production phase. However, full details of the BOM are not reported for confidentiality reasons. Nevertheless, the way the data were processed is explained in detail hereafter.

First, the components were sorted according to the stage in the assembly line they entered. Then composition of the components was taken from the International Material Data System (IMDS). The components were then divided again into large and relevant components and simpler, smaller components. The data on the production of the relevant large components was acquired directly from the suppliers, when available, otherwise by referring to the Environmental Product Declaration (EPD), gray literature or datasheets from EcoInvent. The smaller parts made of the same material and by means of similar manufacturing technologies were summarized and modeled as a single datasheet using EcoInvent datasets that were representative of the average European manufacturing processes. More detailed information on how the material composition was modeled in our study is available in the supplementary material section.

The production of the components included the extraction of raw materials, the transportation of raw materials to a European plant and the manufacturing of the components, assuming average European working conditions.

The energy and gas consumptions were taken from the gas meter and electricity meter at the plant. The consumptions of the last three years were reported on a daily basis. The wastes produced yearly at the plant were listed and reported along with their masses, the European Waste Codes (EWC), the final destinations; the amount of wastewater and their treatment were also given.

As mentioned in section 0, the disposal of wastes in landfills and through incineration was modeled using EcoInvent datasets, whereas only transportation to the platform was considered for wastes sent for recycling.

The main production of the plant is the light-duty vehicle analyzed in this study. As a secondary activity, the manufacturer also produces spare parts for other vehicle types of the same company.

The production time of each version was supplied by the manufacturer: it was slightly less for the Diesel version than for the CNG and Electric version. All the flows that affect the plant were allocated to the three type of vehicles, according to the number of produced vehicles of each version and to its production time.

Distribution

Once the vehicles are finished, they are distributed to the European retailers (UP 10). No primary data were available on sales distribution. For this reason, the same distribution of newly registered LDV cars in Europe for the year 2015 [58] has been hypothesized for the sales of our vehicles; all the produced vehicles were considered sold.

The produced vehicles were transported by means of car transporters, for overland transport, and by means of ships, for maritime transport, and these modes were modeled using the EcoInvent "Transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO4 {RER}" transport,

freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO4 | Alloc Rec, U” and “Transport, freight, sea, transoceanic ship {GLO}| market for | Alloc Rec, U” datasets, respectively.

Operation

Use phase

As far as the use phase is concerned, most LCAs rely on the average kilometric consumption to compare different powertrains. The most common databases present emissions and consumptions divided according to the class of vehicles (Euro 3,4,5...) and to the vehicle typology (passenger car, truck, ...). However, the emissions and consumptions of vehicles are characteristics that depend to a great extent on the vehicle typology and, for the same vehicle category, the driving style can significantly affect the performances. For this reason, a kinematic model, in which the operating conditions of the vehicle were derived from efficiency maps provided by the manufacturer, has been developed in this study. The emissions and consumptions were tailored to the vehicle under study. In order to investigate a wide range of conditions, the performances of the vehicles were analyzed under different driving cycles and considering different load percentages. The validity of the model described in the following paragraph has been proved in previous application [65].

Driving missions

Some reference driving cycles (Artemis, NEDC, WLTP...) and a driving cycle developed ad hoc by the manufacturer were selected from among the driving cycles. The NEDC is a combined chassis dynamometer test used for emission testing and certification in Europe; the NEDC test procedure is going to be replaced with the Worldwide harmonized Light vehicles Test Procedures (WLTP). its Worldwide Harmonized Light Vehicles Test Cycle (WLTC) are chassis dynamometer tests for the determination of emissions and fuel consumption from light-duty vehicles. Artemis Driving Cycles are chassis dynamometer test cycles (urban, rural road and motorway) developed under the Artemis project, based on statistical analysis of European real-world driving conditions. In the present study the urban driving cycle (AUDC) has been considered. The driving cycle "Urban" has been developed ad hoc by the manufacturer for its vehicles' application for urban delivery.

Table 2.2 reports the main specifications of the driving mission sets per each vehicle class (Diesel, CNG and Electric): the duration (s), the length (km), the specific energy consumption (at the wheel level) in traction (SEC-tract) and braking (SEC-brake) stages (kWh/km), the average vehicle speed in traction (km/h), the maximum vehicle speed (km/h) and the average vehicle power demand in traction (kW).

Table 2.2 Main specifications of the two driving missions.

Name	Time [s]	Length [km]	SEC-tract [kWh/km]	SEC-brake [kWh/km]	V-tract [km/h]	V-max [km/h]	P-tract [kW]
NEDC	1180.00	10.34	0.36	-0.34	44.70	80.00	15.98
AUDC	993.00	4.83	0.56	-0.47	25.48	57.70	14.15
URBAN	2583.00	13.48	0.47	-0.42	29.86	75.29	14.07
WLTP-2	1477.00	14.64	0.35	-0.21	44.64	80.00	15.60
WLTP-3	1800.00	20.81	0.40	-0.35	52.01	80.00	20.59

Figure 2.2 depicts the frequency distribution of the power demand of the Diesel vehicle with maximum load over the five driving missions. The AUDC pattern shows a high frequency for low power (close to 0kW) and for high power (40kW for 0% load, 60kW for 100% load). The NEDC distribution instead occurs over the 10-30 kW range.

Figure 2.2 Vehicle power frequency distribution for the two driving missions.

Energy and CO₂ emissions model

The energy model uses a kinematic vehicle approach, where the operating conditions of the system and the control variables are directly obtained with respect to the kinematic state of the system itself. This approach has been implemented in the Matlab environment. This methodology is believed to be consistent with the purpose of this framework, where different vehicle typologies equipped with several powertrains are compared in terms of

energy consumption and CO₂ emissions. The model does not include the effects of transitions, since they have proved to be negligible in the considered driving cycles.

Two different vehicle models have been developed, one for the conventional vehicles (Diesel and CNG), the other for the electric vehicle (BEV).

The power demand to the powertrain is calculated from the vehicle velocity patterns, which is an input to the kinematic model, considering the driveline efficiency chain and the efficiency of each machine (engine, e-machine and battery) as a function of the operating points.

The total power required at the powertrain level, which is the engine for the conventional vehicles and the e-machine for the electric vehicles, is the sum of several components: rolling resistance, grade resistance and drag resistance. If the road is flat, the equation of the power demand is reduced to the following structure:

$$P_v = \left(m_v \cdot g \cdot r_v + \frac{1}{2} (\rho_{air} \cdot c_x \cdot A_v) \cdot v_v^2 + \left(m_v \cdot \frac{N_{wh} \cdot I_{wh}}{R_{wh}} \right) \cdot \dot{v}_v \right) \cdot v_v$$

where m_v is the vehicle mass, g is the gravitational acceleration, r_v is the rolling resistance coefficient of the vehicle (0.008), ρ_{air} is air density (1.22 kg/m³), c_x is the aerodynamic drag coefficient (0.58), A_v vehicle frontal area (3.8 m²), v_v is the vehicle velocity, I_{wh} is the single wheel inertia (1.56 kg m²), N_{wh} is the number of wheels (4), R_{wh} is the dynamic wheel radius (0.35 m) and \dot{v}_v is the vehicle acceleration.

The power at the final-drive level, P_{fd} , is obtained as follows:

$$P_{fd} = \begin{cases} P_v & \text{traction} \\ \gamma_{br} \cdot \gamma_{fr} \cdot P_v & \text{braking} \end{cases}$$

where the factor γ_{fr} represents the power split between the two axles of the vehicle and γ_{br} represents the power share managed by the mechanical frictional brakes during the braking. The two values have been kept constant for all the simulations. The former, γ_{fr} , is set equal to 0 (rear axle fully manages the braking) to maximize the energy recovery for the BEV, the latter, γ_{br} , equal to 0.8 and to 1 for BEVs and any conventional vehicle, respectively, since the vehicle has been tested for standard driving conditions where deceleration manoeuvres are not extreme and the vehicle stability should not be compromised.

The required power at the powertrain level, P_{pt} , is calculated from P_{fd} and the driveline as follows:

$$P_{pt} = (P_{fd} \cdot \varepsilon_{fd}^k + I_{tr} \cdot \omega_{tr} \cdot \dot{\omega}_{tr}) \cdot \varepsilon_{tr}^k + I_{ice} \cdot \omega_{ice} \cdot \dot{\omega}_{ice} + I_{em} \cdot \omega_{em} \cdot \dot{\omega}_{em}$$

where I_{tr} is the transmission inertia, ε_{fd} and ε_{tr} are the efficiency of the final-drive and the transmission, respectively, I_{ice} and I_{em} are the inertia of the internal combustion engine and of the electric machine, respectively, and k is equal to 1 if the vehicle is braking, -1 otherwise. The engine inertial term I_{ice} is 0 for BEVs, while I_{em} is 0 for any conventional powertrain.

Figure 2.3 shows the scheme of the kinematic approach to estimate energy consumption and CO₂ emissions (WTT and TTW). The scheme for Normal Production (NP), regarding Diesel and CNG, is highlighted in yellow. The scheme for the electric version is shown in blue.

Figure 2.3 Scheme of the kinematic approach to estimate energy consumption and CO₂ emissions (WTT and TTW).

Conventional powertrain (Diesel and CNG)

In this section is described the vehicle model used for both Diesel and CNG. The engine speed, ω_{ice} , is a function of the vehicle velocity v_v and the transmission speed ratio τ_{tr} , as follows:

$$\omega_{ice} = \tau_{tr} \cdot \tau_{fd} \cdot \frac{v_v}{R_{wh}}$$

where τ_{fd} is the speed ratio of the final drive and R_{wh} is the dynamic radius of the wheel. The power of the engine P_{ice} is obtained from P_{pt} , where the inertia of the e-machine I_{em} is set to zero:

$$P_{ice} = P_{pt} = (P_{fd} \cdot \varepsilon_{fd}^k + I_{tr} \cdot \omega_{tr} \cdot \dot{\omega}_{tr}) \cdot \varepsilon_{tr}^k + I_{ice} \cdot \omega_{ice} \cdot \dot{\omega}_{ice}$$

The vehicle model checks the operating point of the engine, defined as a (ω_{ice}, P_{ice}) , to be within the engine boundaries, to guarantee the correct functioning of the vehicle.

The engine performance is estimated in terms of fuel consumption. The model employs experimentally-derived quasi-static 2D maps as a function of engine speed and torque, and the mass flow rate of fuel is evaluated by interpolating the 2D map (FCM). **Figure 2.4** shows the efficiency maps of the Diesel engine and CNG engines as a function of torque and speed. High efficiency values are associated to hotter colours (see the aside colour-bar for further

details). The fuel consumption, FC (kg), is then determined by integrating over the driving mission time horizon, as follows:

$$FC = \int_0^T FCM(\omega_{ice}, P_{ice}) \cdot dt$$

Figure 2.4 Diesel (left) and CNG (right) engine efficiency maps as a function of engine torque and speed. (engine torque is normalized for confidentiality reasons).

The corresponding tank-to-wheel (TTW) CO₂ emissions have instead been determined linearly as follows:

$$CO_{2,ttw} = k_{co2,ttw} \cdot FC$$

The $k_{co2,ttw}$ factor was obtained considering a combustion reaction of fuel with air and considering an average fuel composition from literature data. Table 2.3 reports the value for each fuel type in two different units.

Table 2.3 TTW CO₂ conversion factor for different fuels.

Parameter <i>k</i>	Unit	Diesel	CNG
TTW CO ₂	[pound CO ₂ / BTU Fuel]	161.3	117
TTW CO ₂	[kg CO ₂ /kg Fuel]	3.006	2.42
LHV	MWh/kg	12.05	13.42

The corresponding TTW energy consumption has been determined as follows:

$$EC_{ttw} = LHV \cdot FC$$

where LHV represents the lower heating value of the fuel. See Tabl2 2.3 for more details.

The impact of the electric power production is of fundamental importance to properly compare the effective performance in terms of energy consumption and CO₂ emissions of any electric vehicle to that of a conventional vehicle.

Electric powertrain

The electric machine speed, ω_{em} , is a function of the vehicle velocity v_v and the transmission speed ratio τ_{tr} , as follows:

$$\omega_{em} = \tau_{tr} \cdot \tau_{fd} \cdot \frac{v_v}{R_{wh}}$$

where τ_{fd} is the speed ratio of the final drive and R_{wh} is the dynamic radius of the wheel. The power of the e-machine P_{em} is obtained from P_{pt} , where the inertia of the engine is set to zero, as follows:

$$P_{em} = P_{pt} = (P_{fd} \cdot \varepsilon_{fd}^k + I_{tr} \cdot \omega_{tr} \cdot \dot{\omega}_{tr}) \cdot \varepsilon_{tr}^k + I_{em} \cdot \omega_{em} \cdot \dot{\omega}_{em}$$

The vehicle model checks the operating point of the e-machine, defined as a (ω_{em}, P_{em}) , to be within the e-machine boundaries, to guarantee the correct functioning of the vehicle. The electric machine model simulates the power conversion from the mechanical to the electric form, considering the energy losses by means of efficiency maps, which are functions of the machine torque and speed. **Figure 2.5** shows the efficiency map of the e-machine as a function of torque and speed. High efficiency values are associated to hotter colours (see the aside colour-bar for further details). The electric machine efficiency is therefore estimated by interpolating the 2D efficiency map of the e-machine (EEM), as a function of the e-machine mechanical power and speed, as follows:

$$\varepsilon_{em} = EEM(\omega_{em}, P_{em})$$

Figure 2.5 E-machine efficiency map as a function of torque and speed.

The electric power demand of the battery, $P_{bat,el}$, is determined as follows:

$$P_{bat,el} = P_{em} \cdot \varepsilon_{em}^k \cdot \varepsilon_{inv}^k$$

where ε_{inv} is the inverter efficiency and k is equal to 1 if the vehicle is braking, -1 otherwise.

If the powertrain has to provide tractive power, the model checks that P'_{dem} does not exceed the maximum power that the battery can handle. The actual battery power demand is then saturated according to the minimum, $P_{bat,min}$, and maximum, $P_{bat,max}$, battery power, as follows:

$$P_{bat,dem} = \max(\min(P'_{dem}, P_{bat,max}), P_{bat,min})$$

The battery power losses were modeled using an equivalent resistance circuit, in which the resistance and the open-circuit voltage of the battery were State of Charge-dependent. This allowed a lumped representation of more complex chemical processes to be realized. The equilibrium power equation states:

$$P_{bat,chem} = V_{bat} \cdot I_{bat} = P_{bat,dem} + R_{bat} \cdot I_{bat}^2$$

where V_{bat} , I_{bat} , R_{bat} are the voltage, the current and the total resistance of the battery, respectively, and $P_{bat,chem}$ is the chemical battery power demand.

The flowing current is determined solving the above second order polynomial:

$$I_{bat} = \frac{V_{bat} - \sqrt{V_{bat}^2 - 4 \cdot R_{bat} \cdot P_{bat,dem}}}{2 \cdot R_{bat}}$$

The battery temperature is assumed to be constant and the temperature effect is therefore disregarded. The State of Charge (SOC) represents the electrical status of the battery and depends on the equivalent battery capacity and on the flowing current.

$$SOC = SOC_0 - \int \frac{I_{bat}}{C_{bat}} \cdot dt$$

where SOC_0 is the initial SOC of the battery and C_{bat} is the battery capacity (Ah).

FIAMM SONICK batteries require an internal temperature of 270 °C to 350 °C for correct operation. This introduces a constant thermal flow through the battery, due to a temperature gradient with the external environment.

When the battery is not working, the system is partially discharged to power the DC heater to keep the average internal temperature equal to the minimum operating temperature. This energetic loss is reduced with an efficient insulation system, with a thermal conductivity of 0.006W/mK. It has been estimated to be in average as much as 130 W (whether the vehicle is operating or not, or whether it is connected to the grid or not). This

consumption is converted into a specific energy consumption of 0.053 kWh/km for a 28-kWh battery.

The battery energy consumption, BEC (kWh), is determined by the sum of the integral of the battery chemical power $P_{bat,chem}$ over the driving mission time horizon, and the thermal management term as follows:

$$BEC = \frac{1}{3.6e6} \int_0^T P_{bat,chem} \cdot dt + \frac{0.053}{28} \cdot E_{bat} \cdot D_{mis}$$

where E_{bat} is the battery energy content (kWh) and D_{mis} is the driving mission distance (km).

The TTW energy consumption counts also for the charger and battery losses when charging the battery at the end of the trip ($\varepsilon_{bat,RC}$ is the battery efficiency for the given re-charging power), as follows:

$$EC_{ttw} = \frac{BEC}{\varepsilon_{chrg} \cdot \varepsilon_{bat,RC}}$$

Tank to Wheel analysis

Figure 2.6 shows the trend of TTW CO₂ emissions for the two different vehicles (Diesel and CNG) for five driving conditions (coloured bars) and three loads (0%, 50% and 100% of carrying load in left, middle and right charts, respectively). The CO₂ average and standard deviation of each group is reported in red at top and blue at bottom, respectively.

Figure 2.6 TTW CO₂ emissions for three different vehicles for several driving conditions and loads.

Figure 2.7 shows the trend of TTW energy consumption for the three different vehicles (Diesel, CNG and BEV) for five driving conditions (coloured bars) and three loads (0%, 50% and 100% of carrying load in left, middle and right charts, respectively). The electric vehicle is the best solution in terms of energy consumption and reduced it by 50-55% with respect to the Diesel, where higher benefits come at higher loads. It is also less invariant to the driving conditions, since its EC deviation ranges from 20 to 30 Wh/km, against higher values (130-270 Wh/km) of the Diesel counterpart.

Figure 2.7 TTW energy consumption for three different vehicles for several driving conditions and loads.

Table 2.4 reports the efficiency chain comparison between Diesel and BEV over the AUDC with 0% load. The BEV regenerative share was set to 80% for this analysis. The efficiency was calculated as the ratio of the EC at the previous component level to the EC of the current one. For instance, the efficiency at the wheel level of the BEV (80.5%) is the ratio of the vehicle EC (231 Wh/km) to the wheel EC (287 Wh/km).

The efficiency of the Diesel at the wheel level is much lower than that of the BEV, due to the complete loss of the braking energy, 80% of which is instead recovered by the electric vehicle. However, this huge advantage can be halved if the WTT chain is inefficient, as is currently the case in several countries. The Diesel configuration is far better than the CNG counterpart (33-37%), and this aspect has so far determined its extensive adoption.

Table 2.4 Efficiency chain comparison between Diesel and BEV over the AUDC with 0% load.

	Energy Consumption (Wh/km)		Efficiency (-)	
	Diesel	BEV	Diesel	BEV
Vehicle	229	231		
Wheel	378	287	0.606	0.805
Engine/motor	433	298	0.873	0.963
Tank/battery	1207	344	0.359	0.866
BMS	1207	366	1.000	0.940
Plug	1207	472	1.000	0.775
Charger	1207	533	1.000	0.886

Table 2.5 lists the TTW CO₂ emissions and TTW energy consumption of each vehicle for two different delivery missions (M1 and M2). A delivery mission is a sequence of different driving cycles, each with a different vehicle load. Mission M1 represents an urban scenario, where frequent delivery trips are required at part-load. Mission M2 simulates a complete delivery trip, where the weight of the vehicle gradually reduces, due to a series of intermediate delivery stops within the city, and the vehicle returns to the central station by highway with no cargo. The last row of each mission group reports the average of each quantity for a specific vehicle. The electric vehicle reduces TTW energy consumption by 57%. The overall effect of a different mission has been identified to be around 5%, due to the high consumption impact of full load driving conditions. This analysis has highlighted two points of strength of the BEV configuration: 1) different driving missions and vehicle loads affect its performance to a lesser extent than its conventional counterpart; 2) the greatest improvements are achieved under full-load urban driving conditions. However, this vehicle shows the least benefit for non-cargo highway conditions.

Table 2.5 TTW CO₂ emissions and TTW energy consumption for each vehicle for two different delivery missions (M1 and M2).

Mission	Cycle	Load	CO ₂ -ttw (g/km)			EC-ttw (Wh/km)		
			DIE	CNG	BEV	DIE	CNG	BEV
M1	AUDC	50	355.2	349.8	0	1424.5	1934.4	561.1
	AUDC	0	301.1	307.6	0	1207.7	1700.8	515.6
	URB	50	318.1	313.8	0	1275.9	1735.1	540.0
	URB	0	277.2	280.9	0	1111.6	1553.2	506.0
				312.9	313.0	0	1255.0	1730.9
M2	AUDC	100	412.7	399.8	0	1655.2	2210.4	609.4
	URB	100	335.2	327.6	0	1344.6	1811.3	554.1
	AUDC	50	355.2	349.8	0	1424.5	1934.4	561.1
	URB	50	318.1	313.8	0	1275.9	1735.1	540.0
	WLTP	0	224.2	217.0	0	899.3	1199.6	494.5
			329.1	321.6	0	1319.9	1778.2	551.8

Figure 2.8 shows the trend of the TTW energy consumption of the BEV configuration for different regenerative braking factors (0, 40, 60 and 80%), driving conditions (one bar color for each cycle) and vehicle loads (one chart for each load). The default value of the recovery factor is 80%. The total consumption increases by 14% when regenerative braking is completely disabled for an empty vehicle. This increment is even greater for heavier vehicle loads, that is, 20% and 25% for half and full load, respectively. These results prove that braking energy recovery is a key factor for the success of BEVs. To this end, the thermal management of the battery and e-machine and vehicle dynamics to maintain stability during heavy braking when the contribution of the mechanical brakes is minimal will need further development and enhancement to maximize the amount of energy recovery.

The relative impact of regenerative braking at the brake level was compared with that at the TTW level. On average, it drops by about 50%, due to additional losses that reduce its relative importance. For instance, the relative increment of energy consumption of the no-recuperation case, with respect to the 80%-case, is 87% at the brake level for a full-load driving over the AUDC, but it drops to 43% at the TTW level.

Figure 2.8 TTW energy consumption of BEV configuration for different regenerative braking factors, driving conditions and loads.

Other use phase emissions

The model was not used to calculate any other relevant direct emissions (CO, NO_x, PM, etc.), apart from CO₂, because the emission maps contain sensitive data for the manufacturers. However, the manufacturer provided emission data for the vehicle pertaining to the WHTC (*World Harmonized Transient Cycle*), so we extended this information to the other cycles. This implies certain limitations, because emissions are

highly dependent on the driving cycle, and because WHTC is an engine test-bed. The data are reported in Table 2.6. The emissions due to electricity production for the BEV will be discussed in the result section and are reported in Table 74 (supplementary materials).

Table 2.6 Emissions from the WHTC for Diesel and CNG

<i>Emissions</i>	<i>Unit</i>	<i>Diesel</i>	<i>CNG</i>
<i>CO</i>	mg/kWh	58	488,7
<i>NOx</i>	mg/kWh	395	120
<i>PM</i>	mg/kWh	4,9	0,3
<i>HC</i>	mg/kWh	98	-
<i>CH₄</i>	mg/kWh	-	223,7
<i>NMVOOC</i>	mg/kWh	-	2,7
<i>Energy consumption (load 50%)</i>	kWh/km	1.29	1.77

Upstream emissions from electricity production and fuel production have been modelled using the database from EcoInvent: “Diesel {RER}| market group for | Alloc Rec, U” for Diesel; “Natural gas, high pressure {Europe without Switzerland}| market group for | Alloc Rec, U” for natural Gas and “Electricity, low voltage {IT}| market for | Alloc Rec, U” for electricity produced in Italy.

Non exhaust emissions

Non exhaust emissions include particulate matter from tyre wear and brake wear and from abrasion of road surface. They can be significant to an impact assessment because the PM emissions from tyres and brakes largely consist of metals, including significant proportions of heavy metals (Simons, 2016). In EcoInvent 3, emissions are expressed in terms of kg tyre, brake or road abrasion. Non-exhaust emissions per km could thus be scaled directly to vehicle weight, meaning that the emissions had to be defined in terms of kg/kg vehicle and for 1 km (kg/(kg×km)). In this study we have used the values of kg of abrasion /kg vehicle* km from (Simons, 2016) for ICEV vehicles (see values in Table 2.7) and multiplied it for the average Gross Vehicle Weight (GVW) of the different missions analysed (GVW is supposed to vary during the delivery mission, because of the goods delivered along the route).

Table 2.7 Non-exhaust emissions for LDVs

<i>kg of abraded material/(kg vehicle* km)</i>	<i>Diesel</i>	<i>CNG</i>	<i>Electric</i>
<i>Tyres</i>	5.73E-08	5.73E-08	5.73E-08
<i>Brakes</i>	4.45E-09	4.45E-09	8.9E-10
<i>Road</i>	9.79E-09	9.79E-09	9.79E-09

The road wear and tire wear were considered to be the same for ICEV and BEV (per kg) since the wear is dependent only on the mass of the vehicle in the literature [60]. For brake emissions a literature value that estimate brake emissions from BEV to be 20% less than their ICEV counterpart has been assumed. the reduced emission is due to regenerative braking, which causes mechanical brakes are used considerably less [60]. The uncertainty related to the use of literature data has been included in the uncertainty analysis.

Maintenance and components replacement

As a result of the limited relevance of maintenance, as established from literature in [61] and [25], this stage has been disregarded in many LCA studies. Moreover, maintenance is unpredictable, as it depends on the individual user's behavior and on environmental conditions, and it can change considerably from case to case. Some of the few authors who have accounted for it used generic data as scaling factors [61], or average data taken from literature [6].

However, since the complexity of vehicles is expected to grow, the impact associated with maintenance is also expected to grow. The maintenance of EVs is expected to be lower than that of ICEVs [62]. It has been hypothesized that BEVs will cause less wear of the brake pads and disks as confirmed in [60], and all the typical replacements of ICEVs, such as that of the oil, oil filters, spark plugs, timing belts and fuel filters, will be avoided. All the repairs needed for the exhaust system will also become unnecessary.

In this study, the data on maintenance and component replacement have been provided by the manufacturer for the Diesel version, and the CNG has been assumed to be the same as that of a Diesel vehicle.

Maintenance was modeled considering: 1. the frequency of the replacements of the components and parts provided by the manufacturer; 2. the production of the replacement parts as being the same as the production of the originals; 3. the consumptions and emissions due to replacement operations could be disregarded

Table 2.8 Maintenance operations and their frequency

<i>Maintenance Operation</i>	<i>Diesel</i>	<i>CNG</i>	<i>Electric</i>
<i>Oil change</i>	Every 40.000 km	Every 40.000 km	-
<i>Oil filter change</i>	Every 40.000 km	Every 40.000 km	-
<i>Timing belt change</i>	Every 60.000 km	Every 60.000 km	-
<i>Alternator belt</i>	Every 60.000 km	Every 60.000 km	-
<i>Fuel filter change</i>	Every 40.000 km	Every 40.000 km	-
<i>Brake fluid change</i>	Every 60.000 km	Every 60.000 km	Every 60.000 km
<i>Air filter change</i>	Every 40.000 km	Every 40.000 km	-
<i>Cooling fluid change</i>	Every 120.000 km	Every 120.000 km	-
<i>Lead Battery change</i>	Once	Once	-
<i>Tires substitution</i>	Three times	Three times	Three times
<i>NaNiCl Battery</i>	-	-	-

The brake fluid change and tire substitution for the electric version were assumed to have the same frequency as the ICEV versions. As a first assumption, the battery lifetime was considered to be the same as the vehicle lifetime.